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ENVRI Glossary

The ENVRI Glossary contains terms, abbreviations and acronyms used in the environmental community.
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Acronym	Definition
14C	Radiocarbon
14CO2	Carbon dioxide containing a heavy isotope of carbon
A	
a/c	Aircraft
AA	Attribute Authority
AAAI	Authentication, Authorisation, and Accounting Infrastructure
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure / Authentication and Authorisation Interface
AARC	Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration (a series of EC-funded projects)
AARC/GEANT	Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration / Gigabit European Academic Network
AAS	Australian Academy of Science
ABCD	Access to Biological Collection Data
AC	Active Collab (a Project Management System)
ACBB	Agroecosystems, Biogeochemical Cycles and Biodiversity
Access Control	A functionality that approves or disapproves of access requests based on specified access policies
ACDD	Attribute Convention for Data Discovery (for NetCDF)
Acquisition Service	Oversight service for integrated data acquisition
Active role	An active role is typically associated with a human actor
ACTRIS	Aerosols, Clouds, and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure Network
Add Metadata	Add additional information according to a predefined schema (metadata schema). This partially overlaps with data annotations
ADM-AEOLUS	Atmospheric Dynamics Mission Aeolus (ADM-Aeolus), is an Earth observation satellite operated by the European Space Agency (ESA)
AF	Air France / Analytical Framework
AFO2000	Atmosphärenforschung 2000

AGA	Amendment of the Grant Agreement -> see also AMD
AGU	American Geophysical Union
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIP	Archival Information Package
AIRBUS	Airbus Operations SAS
AISBL	Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif (International non-profit association under Belgian Law)
ALADIN	Atmospheric Laser Doppler Instrument (Payload of ADM-AEOLUS)
ALLAS	Equipment of an airplane of Lufthansa for long-term detection of atmospheric trace gases
AMD	AMenDment
AMDAR	Aircraft Meteorological Data Relay
AnaEE	RI on Analysis and Experimentation on Ecosystems
AnaeeThes	AnaEE Thesaurus
Annotate Data	Annotate data with meaning (concepts of predefined local or global conceptual models)
Annotate Metadata	Link metadata with meaning (concepts of predefined local or global conceptual models). This can be done by adding a pointer to concepts within a conceptual model to the data.
Annotation	(verb) The action of annotating or adding notes (noun) A note added to anything written, by way of explanation or comment
Annotation Service	Oversight service for adding and updating records attached to curated datasets
AOGS	Asia Oceania Geosciences Society
API	Application Programming Interface, is a set of routines, protocols, and tools for building software applications
AQUA	Earth Observing Satellite (launched on May 4, 2002)
AQUACOSM	EU network of mesocosms facilities for research on marine and freshwater ecosystems open for global collaboration
ARDC	Australian Research Data Commons

ARISE	Atmospheric dynamics Research InfraStructure in Europe
Assign Unique Identifier	Obtain a unique identifier and associate with the data
ATC	Atmospheric Thematic Centre of ICOS
ATLID	Cloud-Aerosol High-Spectral Resolution Lidar (Payload of EARTHCARE)
ATMO	HGF Programme Atmosphere and Climate
ATMOSAT	Atmospheric Satellite in Planning AURA Earth Observing Satellite (launched on July 15, 2004)
AuScope	Australian geoscience programme
Authentication	A functionality that verifies a credential of a user
Authentication Service	Security service responsible for the authentication of external agents making requests of infrastructure services
Authorisation	A functionality that specifies access rights to resources
Authorisation Service	Security service responsible for the authorisation of all requests made of infrastructure services by external agents
B	
B2HANDLE	EUDAT minting, storing, managing and accessing persistent identifiers
B2SAFE	EUDAT Data Storage and Distribution System
B2SHARE	EUDAT Data Sharing Platform
BA	British Airways plc
Backup	A copy of (persistent) data so it may be used to restore the original after a data loss event.
BADM	Biological, Ancillary, Disturbance and Metadata
BCO	Biological Collections Ontology
BCP	Backscatter Cloud Probe
BDD	Behaviour-Driven Development
BEERi	Board of European Environmental Research Infrastructures - an internal advisory board representing the needs of environmental Research Infrastructures (from 2024 on: ENVRI Board)
Biodiversity	The variety of different types of life found on earth

Biodiversity metrics	Measurements of the number of species and how they are distributed
BioMA	Biophysical Model Applications
BIOS	BioSense Institute - Research and Development Institute for Information Technologies in Biosystems
BL	Belgian non-profit association (legal entity type)
BMBF	Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung
BODC	British Oceanographic Data Centre
BPA	BluePrint Architecture or the AARC
BRGM	Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières
Build Conceptual Models	Establish a local or global model of interrelated concepts
C	
CA	1) Consortium Agreement - Legal contract between the project beneficiaries 2) Certification Authority
CAL	1) China Airlines 2) ICOS Central Analytical Laboratory
calculations	Calculation refers to the process of using quantitative methods—formulas, measurements, and models—to derive numerical results or predictions.
CALIPSO	Cloud-Aerosol Lidar and Infrared Pathfinder Satellite Observations Satellite (launched in April 28, 2006)
Cal-Val	Calibration and Validation
CAMAACC	Civil aircraft for regular investigation of the atmosphere based on an instrument container
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
Capacity Manager	An active role, which is a person who manages and ensures that the IT capacity meets current and future business requirements in a cost-effective manner
CARE-C	Climate and Atmosphere Research Center
CARIBIC	Civil Aircraft for the Regular Investigation of the Atmosphere Based on an Instrument Container

Carry out Backup	Replicate data to an additional data storage so it may be used to restore the original after a data loss event. A special type of backup is a long-term preservation.
CAS	1) Central Authentication Service 2) Chemical Abstract Service
Catalogue (Metadata)	A collection of metadata, usually established to make the metadata available to a community. A metadata catalogue has an access service.
Catalogue service	Oversight service for cataloguing curated datasets
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
CC0-1.0	Creative Commons Zero v1.0 Universal
CC4BY license	Creative Commons license with attribution alone (BY) according to the version 4.0 (international jurisdiction)
CC-BY	Creative Commons Attribution License, a standardised way to grant the public permission to use creative work under copyright law.
CC-BY-4.0	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
CCSDS	Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems
CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
CDI	Common Data Index
CEA	Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique et aux Énergies Alternatives
CEOS	Committee on Earth Observation Satellites
CERIF	Common European Research Information Format (an EU Recommendation to Member States)
CETAF	Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities
CF	Climate and Forecast (semantics for NetCDF)
CFC	Chlorofluorocarbon
CFs	ICOS Central Facilities, i.e., ATC, ETC, OTC, CAL
CGP	Company CGP Associates Ltd., UK
CH4	Methane
Check Quality	Actions to verify the quality of data

Chl a	Chlorophyll a
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment
CIARD RING	A global directory of information services and datasets in agriculture
CINECA	Consorzio Interuniversitario CNR: Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche
Citation	from the ENVRI RM perspective, citation is defined as a pointer from a publication to: data source(s); and/or the owner(s) of the data source(s); a description of the evaluation process, if available; a timestamp marking the access time to the data sources, thus reflecting a certain version
Citizen Scientist	An active role, member of the general public who engages in scientific work, often in collaboration with or under the direction of professional scientists and scientific institutions (also known as amateur scientist)
CKAN	Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network
CLOUDSAT	Satellite with first satellite-based millimeter-wavelength cloud radar (launched in April 28,2006)
CLRTAP	Convention on Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution
CLS	Collecte Localisation Satellite
CMCC	Fondazione Centro euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (Euro-Mediterranean Centre on Climate Change)
CMDI	Component MetaData Infrastructure
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
CMIS	Content Management Interoperability Services
CNECT	Communications Networks, Content and Technology
CNES	Centre National d'Études Spatiales
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
CNRS-LA	CNRS-Laboratoire d'Aérodologie
CNRS-SA	CNRS-Service d'Aéronomie
CO	Carbon Monoxide

CO2	Carbon Dioxide
COAR	Confederation of Open Access Repositories
CODATA	Committee on Data for Science and Technology
co-design	Participatory design (originally co-operative design, now often co-design) is an approach to design attempting to actively involve all stakeholders (e.g. employees, partners, customers, citizens, end users) in the design process to help ensure the result meets their needs and is usable.
Community	A collaboration which consists of a set of roles agreeing their objective to achieve a stated business purpose
Community Behaviour	A behaviour of a community is a composition of actions performed by roles normally addressing separate business requirements
Concept	Name and definition of the meaning of a thing (abstract or real thing), human readable definition by sentences, machine readable definition by relations to other concepts (machine readable sentences)
Conceptual Model	A collection of concepts, their attributes and their relations. It can be unstructured or structured (e.g. glossary, thesaurus, ontology). Usually the description of a concept and/or a relation defines the concept in a human readable form.
Confluence	A popular web-based corporate wiki (collaboration software) developed by Australian software company Atlassian
ConnectinGEO	Coordinating an Observation Network of Networks EnCompassing saTellite and IN-situ to fill the Gaps in European Observations
CONTRAIL	Comprehensive Observation Network for Trace gases by Air-Liners
COOP+	Cooperation of Research Infrastructures to address global challenges in the environmental field, a Horizon 2020 project
COOPEUS	Strengthening the cooperation between the US and the EU in the field of environmental research infrastructures
Coordination Service	An oversight service for data processing tasks deployed on infrastructure execution resources
COP	The informal name for the Conference of the Parties to the United Nations' Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)
COPDESS	Coalition for Publishing Data on the Earth and Space Sciences

COPERNICUS	Previously known as GMES (Global Monitoring for Environment and Security), is the European Union's Earth observation programme coordinated and managed by the European Commission in partnership with the European Space Agency (ESA), the EU Member States and EU Agencies
CoreTrustSeal	A certification organisation which offers to any interested data repository a core level certification based on the DAS–WDS Core Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements catalogue and procedures
CoS	(ENVRI-Hub) Catalogue of Services
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019 is an infectious disease caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2.
CP	Carbon Portal
CPA	Cathay Pacific Airways
CPC	Condensation Particle Counter
CPR	Cloud Profiling Radar (Payload of EARTHCARE)
CREA	Consiglio per la Ricerca in Agricoltura e l'analisi dell'Economia Agraria
CRL	1) Certificate Revocation List 2) Central Radiocarbon Laboratory of CAL
Crossdisciplinary	Viewing one discipline from the perspective of another
CSIC	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas
CSIRO	Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation
CSR	1) Corporate Social Responsibility 2) Certificate Signing Request
CSW	Catalogue Service for the Web
CTP	Community Training Portal
CTS	CoreTrustSeal
CU	Cardiff University
cURL	An application library for transferring data with URLs
Cyl	Cyprus Institute

D

D	Deliverable
D4Science	An organisation offering a Hybrid Data Infrastructure service and a number of Virtual Research Environments
DANS	Data Archiving and Networked Services
DANUBIUS	International Center for Advanced Studies on River –Delta – Sea Systems, a Research Infrastructure
DANUBIUS-RI	International Center for Advanced Studies on River –Delta – Sea Systems Research Infrastructure
DARE	Delivering Agile Research Excellence on European e-Infrastructures H2020 project
DAS	Data Acquisition System
DASSH	Data Archive for Seabed Species (a UK marine biology resource centre)
Data Acquisition Community	A community, which collects raw data and brings (streams of) measures into a system
Data Analysis	A functionality that inspects, cleans, transforms data, and provides data models with the goal of highlighting useful information, suggesting conclusions, and supporting decision making
Data Assimilation	A functionality that combines observational data with output from a numerical model to produce an optimal estimate of the evolving state of the system
Data Broker	Broker for facilitating data access/upload requests
Data Cataloguing	A functionality that associates a data object with one or more metadata objects which contain data descriptions
Data Citation	A functionality that assigns an accurate, consistent and standardised reference to a data object, which can be cited in scientific publications
Data Collection	A behaviour performed by a data collector which controls and monitors the collection of the digital values from a sensor instrument or a human sensor, such as a measurer or an observer, associating consistent time-stamps and necessary metadata
Data Collector	Active or passive role, adopted by a person or an instrument collecting data

Data Curation Subsystem	A subsystem that facilitates quality control and preservation of scientific data.
Data Curation Community	A community, which curates the scientific data, maintains and archives them, and produces various data products with metadata
Data Curator	An active role, which is a person who verifies the quality of the data, preserves and maintains the data as a resource, and prepares various required data products.
Data Discovery & Access	A functionality that retrieves requested data from a data resource by using a suitable search technology
Data Exporter	Binding object for exporting curated datasets
Data Extraction	A functionality that retrieves data out of (unstructured) data sources, including web pages, emails, documents, PDFs, scanned text, mainframe reports, and spool files
Data Identification	A functionality that assigns (global) unique identifiers to data contents
Data Importer	An oversight service for the import of new data into the data curation subsystem
Data infrastructure	A collection of data assets, organisations that operate and maintain them and guides describing how to use and manage the data. A data infrastructure is sustainably funded and has oversight that provides direction to maximise data use and value by meeting the needs of society. A data infrastructure includes technology, processes and organisation.
Data management	A process for managing the data lifecycle needs of a specific research community
Data management plan (DMP)	A formal document that outlines how data are to be handled both during a research project and after the project is completed
Data Mining	A functionality that supports the discovery of patterns in large data sets
Data Originator	Either an active or a passive role, which provides the digital material to be made available for public access
Data pipeline	In computing, a pipeline is a set of data processing elements connected in series, where the output of one element is the input of the next one.

Data Processing Control	A functionality that initiates the calculation and manages the outputs to be returned to the client
Data Processing Subsystem	A subsystem that aggregates the data from various resources and provides computational capabilities and capacities for conducting data analysis and scientific experiments.
Data Product Generation	A functionality that processes data against requirement specifications and standardised formats and descriptions
Data Provenance	Information that traces the origins of data and records all state changes of data during their lifecycle and their movements between storages
Data Provider	Either an active or a passive role, which is an entity providing the data to be used.
Data Publication	A functionality that provides clean, well-annotated, anonymity-preserving datasets in a suitable format, and by following specified data-publication and sharing policies to make the datasets publicly accessible or to those who agree to certain conditions of use, and to individuals who meet certain professional criteria
Data Publication Repository	A passive role, which is a facility for the deposition of published data
Data Publication Community	A community that assists the data publication, discovery and access
Data Publishing Subsystem	A subsystem that enables discovery and retrieval of data housed in data resources
Data Quality Checking	A functionality that detects and corrects (or removes) corrupt, inconsistent or inaccurate records from data sets
Data Service Provision Community	A community that provides various services, applications and software/tools to link, and recombine data and information in order to derive knowledge
Data State	Term used as defined in ISO/IEC 10746-2. At a given instant in time, data state is the condition of an object that determines the set of all sequences of actions (or traces) in which the object can participate.
Data Store Controller	A data store within the data curation subsystem
Data stream	A sequence of digitally encoded coherent signals used to transmit or receive information that is in the process of being transmitted

Data Transfer Service	Oversight service for the transfer of data into and out of the data curation subsystem
Data Transmission	A functionality that transfers data over communication channels using specified network protocols
Data Transporter	Generic binding object for data transfer interactions
Data Use Subsystem	A subsystem that provides functionalities to manage, control, and track users' activities and supports users to conduct their roles in the community
Data Use Community	A community who makes use of the data and service products, and transfers the knowledge into understanding
Data Acquisition Subsystem	A subsystem that collects raw data and brings the measures or data streams into a computational system
Data Consumer	Either an active or passive role, which is an entity who receives and uses the data.
Data Storage & Preservation	A functionality that deposits (over long-term) the data and metadata or other supplementary data and methods according to specified policies, and makes them accessible on request
DataCite	An international not-for-profit organisation which aims to improve data citation
DataOne	Data Observation Network for Earth
DC	Data Centre
DCAT	Data Catalogue Vocabulary
DCAT (JSON-LD)	Data Catalogue Vocabulary (JSON for Linking Data)
DCAT-AP	Data Catalogue Vocabulary - Application Profile
DCC	Digital Curation Centre
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DDS	Data Distribution Service
DDSS	Data, Data products, Software and Services
DEIMS-SDR	Dynamic Ecological Information System Site and Dataset Registry

Describe Service	Describe the accessibility of a service or process, which is available for reuse, the interfaces, the description of behaviour and/or implemented algorithms
Design of Measurement Model	A behaviour that designs the measurement or monitoring model based on scientific requirements
Designer	Measurement Model Designer; an active role, which is a person who designs the measurements and monitoring models based on the requirements of (environmental) scientists
DevOps	Set of practices that combines software development (Dev) and IT operations (Ops). It aims to shorten the systems development life cycle and provides continuous delivery with high software quality; complementary with Agile software development; several DevOps aspects came from Agile methodology.
DEVSECOPS	DevSecOps is an augmentation of DevOps to allow for security practices to be integrated into the DevOps approach. The traditional centralised security team model must adopt a federated model allowing each delivery team the ability to factor in the correct security controls into their DevOps practices.
DG	Director(ate) General
DIAS	Copernicus Data and Information Access Services
DIP	Dissemination Information Package
DIRAC	Distributed Infrastructure with Remote Agent Control
DiSSCo	Distributed System of Scientific Collections
DKRZ	Deutsches KlimaRechenZentrum GmbH
DLC	Data LifeCycle
DLH	Deutsche Lufthansa AG
DLR	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt
DMC	Data and Modeling Centre of the AnaEE Research Infrastructure
DMP	1) Data Management Plan 2) Data Management Platform
DMSF	Document Management System Features
DMT	1) Data Management Team 2) Droplet Measurement Technologies, USA

DNS	Domain Name Server
Do Data Mining	Execute a sequence of metadata / data request --> interpret result --> do a new request
DoA	Description of Action, synonym to DoW
DOAS	Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy
DocDB	Document Database
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DOIP	Digital Object Interface Protocol
DOM	Document Object Model (DOM) is the data representation of the objects that comprise the structure and content of a document on the web.
DoW	Description of Work, synonym to DoA
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DRIP	Dynamic Real-time Infrastructure Planner
DRIS	Directory of Research Information Systems
DS	Design Study
DSA	Data Seal of Approval
DSB	Development Steering Board
DSM	Digital Single Market
DSW	Data Stewardship Wizard
DWD	Deutscher Wetterdienst
DXWG	Data Exchange Working Group
E	
EAA	Environment Agency Austria (Umweltbundesamt GmbH)
EAB	ICOS Ethical Advisory Board
E-ADAS	E-AMDAR Data Acquisition System
E-AMDAR	EUMETNET-AMDAR

EAP	EOSC Earlier Adopter Programme
EARLINET	European Aerosol Research Lidar Network
EARSC	European Association of Remote Sensing Companies
EARTHCARE	Earth Cloud Aerosol and Radiation Explorer
EarthCube	Community of scientists across all geoscience domains, as well as geoinformatics researchers and data scientists
EASA	European Aviation Safety Agency
EB	1) Executive Board - supervisory body for the execution of the Project 2) Ethical Board
EBV	Essential Biodiversity Variable(s)
EC	European Commission
ECATS	Environmental Compatible Air Transport System
ECHAM	Atmospheric General Circulation Model
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium Range Weather Forecast
ECO	EPOS Coordination Office
ECR	Ethics Compliance Report
ECV	Essential Climate Variable(s)
eddy covariance technique	The eddy covariance (also known as eddy correlation and eddy flux) technique is a key atmospheric measurement technique to measure and calculate vertical turbulent fluxes within atmospheric boundary layers.
EDI	European Data Infrastructure
EDIOS	European Directory of the Initial Ocean-Observing Systems
EDMED	European Directory of Marine Environmental Data sets
EDMERP	European Directory of Marine Environmental Research Projects
EDMO	European Directory of Marine Organisations
Educator	An active role, which is a person who makes use of the data and application services for education and training purposes (synonym: Trainer)

EduGAIN	An international identity service interconnecting research and education identity federations
EEA	European Environment Agency
EERT	Extended Entity-Relationship modelling with Temporal aspects
EEV	Essential Ecosystem Variables
EFG	Access to Biological Collection Databases Extended for Geosciences
EFIS	European Future Innovation System
EGDI	European Geological Data Infrastructure
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure
EGIM	EMSO Generic Instrument Module
EGU	European Geosciences Union
EGV	Essential Geodetic Variable(s)
EHN	ENVRI-Hub NEXT
EH-VRE	Virtual Research Environment created for ENVRI-Hub
EIDA	European Integrated Data Archive
EIH	ENVRI Innovation Hub
eInfraCentral	European e-Infrastructure Services Gateway
e-Infrastructure	A combination and interworking of digitally-based technology (hardware and software), resources (data, services, digital libraries), communications (protocols, access rights and networks), and the people and organisational structures needed to support modern, internationally leading collaborative research be it in the arts and humanities or the sciences
e-IRG	e-Infrastructure Reflection Group
EIROforum	European Intergovernmental Research Organisation Forum
EISCAT	European Incoherent Scatter Scientific Association
EISCAT_3D	European three-dimensional imaging radar for atmospheric and geospace research
Elastic Search	Elasticsearch is a search engine based on the Lucene library.

ELIXIR	An intergovernmental organisation that brings together life science resources from across Europe. These resources include databases, software tools, training materials, cloud storage and supercomputers.
eLTER	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research Infrastructure
eLTER CDN	eLTER Central Data Node
eLTER DIP	eLTER Data Integration Portal
EMAC	ECHAM/MESSy Atmospheric Chemistry Model
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EMBRC	European Marine Biological Resource Centre
EML	Environmental Markup Language / Ecological Metadata Language
EMODNET	European Marine Observation and Data NETWORK
EMPHASIS	Effective Management of Pests and Harmful Alien Species - Integrated Solutions, a H2020 project
EMRP	European Metrology Research Programme
EMSC	Euro-Mediterranean Seismological Centre
EMSO	European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and Water Column Observatory
EMSO DMP	EMSO Data Management Platform
EMSO ERIC	European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and Water Column Observatory - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ENEP	European Network of Environmental Professionals
Engineer	An active role, which is a person who develops and maintains the research infrastructure (synonym: Technologist).
ENRIITC	European Network of Research Infrastructures & Industry for Collaboration
ENV	Environment(al)
ENV SWG ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures - Strategic Working Group on Environment
Environmental Scientist	An active role, which is a person who conducts research or performs investigations for the purpose of identifying, abating, or eliminating

	sources of pollutants or hazards that affect either the environment or the health of the population, using knowledge of various scientific disciplines, may collect, synthesize, study, report, and recommend action based on data derived from measurements or observations of air, food, soil, water, and other sources
ENVISAT	Earth Observation Satellite (launched in 2002, operation ceased in 2012)
ENVRI	1) (The ENVRI Community of) Environmental Research Infrastructures. 2) FP7 project on Implementation of common solutions for a cluster of ESFRI infrastructures in the field of Environmental Sciences.
ENVRI Board	Board of European Environmental Research Infrastructures - an internal advisory board representing the needs of environmental Research Infrastructures (before 2024: BEERi)
ENVRI Cluster	A group of environmental research infrastructures collaborating in the project – currently 12 ESFRI research infrastructures)
ENVRI Community	A community of 26 Environment research infrastructures (on ESFRI level or upcoming)
ENVRI KB	ENVRI Knowledge Base
ENVRI Reference Model	A common ontological framework and standards for the description and characterisation of computational and storage systems of ESFRI environmental research infrastructures
ENVRI week	ENVRI consortium meeting
ENVRI_RM	ENVRI Reference Model
ENVRI-FAIR	ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES BUILDING FAIR SERVICES ACCESSIBLE FOR SOCIETY, INNOVATION AND RESEARCH, A HORIZON 2020 PROJECT
ENVRI-Hub	A federated machine-to-machine interface for ENVRI data and services
ENVRI-ID	ENVRI-IDentifier
ENVRINNOV	Environment Research Infrastructures Innovation Roadmap
ENVRIplus	ENVRIplus is a Horizon 2020 project bringing together Environmental and Earth System Research Infrastructures, projects and networks together with technical specialist partners to create a more coherent,

	interdisciplinary and interoperable cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures across Europe.
EnvThes	Environmental Thesaurus
EO	Earth Observation
EOS	Earth Observing System
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-Hub	A Horizon 2020 project for Integrating and managing services for the European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-LIFE	EOSC cluster for the biological and medical Ris
EOSCpilot	European Open Science Cloud for Research Pilot Project, a Horizon 2020 project
EOSCSecretariat	A Horizon 2020 project which delivers 360° support to the EOSC Governance while working with communities to co-create an all-encompassing European Open Science
EOV	Essential Ocean Variable(s)
ePIC	electronic Publication Information Center
EPOS	European Plate Observation System
EPOS ERIC	European Plate Observation System European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EPOS ICS-C	European Plate Observing System Integrated Core Services - C
EPOSAR	Level1 service, based on the Small BAseLine Subset (SBAS) SInSAR technique, allows both on demand and automatic generation of ground displacement map and time series
EPOS-DCAT-AP	DCAT Application Profile for EPOS, EPOS extension of DCAT-AP
ERA	European Research Area
ERDDAP	NOAA developed science data server technology that gives a simple, consistent way to download subsets of gridded and tabular scientific datasets in common file formats and make graphs and map
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium (legal entity type)
ERIS	Environmental Research Infrastructures Strategy for 2030

ESA	European Space Agency
ESCAPE	European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle physics ESFRI research infrastructures
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ESFRI-ENV RI	ESFRI Environmental Research Infrastructure
ESIF	European Structural and Investment Funds
ESIP	Earth Science Information Partners
ESO	European Southern Observatory
ESONET Vi	European Seafloor Observatory NETwork - The Vision
ESSI	Earth and Space Science (e)Infrastructures
ETC	Ecosystem Thematic Centre of ICOS
ETHER	Thematic Assembly Center of CNES
ETHZ	Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich
ETS	Emission Trading Scheme
EU	European Union
EUA	1) Europäische Umweltagentur 2) European University Association
EUDAT	European Collaborative Data Infrastructure or EUDAT CDI
EUFAR	European Facility for Airborne Research
EUMETNET	Network of 31 European National Meteorological Services
EURO-ARGO	European ARGO programme (ARGO are a type of marine survey device)
EURO-ARGO ERIC	EURO-ARGO European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EurOBIS	European Ocean Biogeographic Information System
EUROCHAMP2020	European atmospheric simulation chambers
EUROFLEETS	New operational steps towards an alliance of European research fleets
EuroGOOS	European Global Ocean Observing System

EuroSITES	European Ocean Observatory Network
EUSAAR	European Supersites for Atmospheric Aerosol Research
EV	Essential Variable
EVERSE	European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence
Experiment Laboratory	Community proxy for conducting experiments within a research infrastructure
EXV	Essential Variable(s), concepts in domains such as Climate, Ocean and Biodiversity sciences
F	
F2F	face to face
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (of digital assets)
FAIR + R	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable + Reproducible
FAIR principles	principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
FAIR4Health	Improving Health Research in EU through FAIR Data, a Horizon 2020 project
FAIRsFAIR	Fostering FAIR Data Practices in Europe, a Horizon 2020 project
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
FCL	Flask and Calibration Laboratory of CAL
FDO	FAIR Data Object
FDP	FAIR Data Point (instance)
Field Laboratory	Community proxy for interacting with data acquisition instruments
FIM4R	Federated Identity Management for Research collaborations
Final review	Review the data to be published, which will not likely be changed again
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
FITSM	The name for a family of standards for lightweight IT service management (ITSM).
FixO3	Fixpoint Open Ocean Observatories (survey programme)

FLUXNET	global network of micrometeorological tower sites
FMI	Finnish Meteorological Institute (Ilmatieteen Laitos)
FORC	Future of Research Communication
FORCE11	Future of Research and Communications and e-Scholarships
FOS	Fixed Ocean Stations
FP	Framework Programme
Free text annotation	to add a short explanation or opinion to a text or drawing (equivalent to the dictionary definition of annotation)
FREYA	Connected Open Identifiers for Discovery, Access and Use of Research Resources project
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
FZJ	Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH
G	
G3W	WMO Global Greenhouse Gas Watch
GA	1) Grant Agreement - Contract between Coordinator and Commission 2) General Assembly - GA is the ultimate decision making body of the consortium
GAI	Green Area Index
GAMS	GMES Atmospheric Monitoring Service
GAS	GMES Atmospheric Service
GAW	Global Atmospheric Watch
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GCC	GMES Climate Service
GCMD	Global Change Master Directory
GCMD DIF	Global Change Master Directory Directory Interchange Format
GCOS	Global Climate Observing System
gCube	An open-source software toolkit used for building and operating Hybrid Data Infrastructures enabling the dynamic deployment of

	Virtual Research Environments by favouring the realisation of reuse oriented policies
GDAC	Global Data Assembly Center
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation, a regulation in EU law on data protection and privacy in the European Union and the European Economic Area.
GDSN	Global Data Synchronisation Network
GEANT	NRENs have formed the GÉANT Association, an organisation for European collaboration in research networks.
GEMET	GEneral Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus
GEO	Group on Earth Observations, that coordinates international efforts to build a Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS) / Global Earth Observation
GEO-C	Group on Earth Observations-Carbon
GeoDCAT	Geospatial extension of DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)
GEOECOMAR	Institutul National de Cercetare-Dezvoltare pentru Geologie si Geoecologie Marina
GeoERA	Establishing the European Geological Surveys Research Area to deliver a Geological Service for Europe, a Horizon 2020 project
GEOMAR	Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems coordinated by GEO (The Group on Earth Observations)
GEP	Geohazards Exploitation Platform
GERI	Global Ecosystem Research Infrastructure
GES	Good Environmental Status
GFM	Gomolzig Flugzeug- und Maschinenbau GmbH
GHG	GreenHouse Gas
GIS	Geographic Information System
GitHub	United States-based global company that provides hosting for software development version control using Git

GLODAP	Global Ocean Data Analysis Product
GMES	Global Monitoring for Environment and Security
GNI	Gross National Income
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GO FAIR	A bottom-up international initiative for FAIR data for the practical implementation of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) (synonym: GOFAIR)
GO INTER	Active GO FAIR Implementation Network
GOFAIR	EU initiative for FAIR data (synonym: GO FAIR)
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
GOOS BGC	GOOS BioGeoChemistry panel
GOSAT	Greenhouse Gases Observing Satellite (launched January 23, 2009)
GO-SHIP	Global Ocean Ship-based Hydrographic Investigations Programm
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GROOM	Gliders for Research Ocean Observation and Management
GSF	Global Science Forum
GSM	Global System for Mobile Communications
GSN	Global Seismographic Network
GTOS	Global Terrestrial Observing System
GUI	A GUI (graphical user interface) is a system of interactive visual components for computer software.
GUPRI	Global Unique Persistent and Referable Identifier
H	
H2	Hydrogen
H2020	Horizon 2020, European Research and Innovation funding programme
HE	Horizon Europe, a European funding work programme
HEI	Higher Education Institutions

HELIX Nebula	Partnership between big science and big business in Europe that is charting the course towards the sustainable provision of cloud computing - the Science Cloud
HEMERA	Integrated access to balloon-borne platforms for innovative research and technology, a H2020 project
HGF	Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft Deutscher Forschungszentren
HLEG	High Level Expert Group
HO	1) ICOS Head Office 2) Hosting Organisation (of EPOS)
HPC	High Performance Computing
HTAP	Task Force on Hemispheric Transport of Air Pollution
HTC	High Throughput Computing
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
I	
I3	Integrated Infrastructures Initiative (I3) combines several activities essential to reinforce research infrastructures and to provide an integrated service at the European level.
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
I-ADOPT	Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology
IAGOS AISBL	In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System (funded 2014)
IAGOS-DS	Integration of Routine Aircraft Measurements into a Global Observing System – Design Study
IAGOS-ERI	In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System – European Research Infrastructure
IASI	Infrared Atmospheric Sounding Interferometer (Payload on METOP-A/B/C)
IB	Iberia, spanish airline company
ICH	1) International Council for Harmonisation 2) Integrated Circuit Humidity (sensor)
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System
ICOS ERIC	ICOS European Research Infrastructure Consortium

ICOS RI	ICOS Research Infrastructure
ICOS2020SC	ICOS Science Conference 2020
ICS-C	Integrated Core Services - Central Hub
ICS-D	Integrated Core Services - Distributed
ICSU	International Council of Science
ICSU-WDS	International Council for Science - World Data System
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IDF	International DOI Foundation
IdP	Identity Provider
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IEEE LOM	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Learning Objects Metadata
IEK-8	Institut für Energie und Klimaforschung: Troposphäre
IFREMER	Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer
IFT	Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research
IG	Interest Group
IG3IS	Integrated Global Greenhouse Gas Information System
IGACO	Integrated Global Atmospheric Chemistry Observations
IGAS	IAGOS for the GMES Atmospheric Service
IGBP	International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme
IGCO	Integrated Global Carbon Observation Theme
IGTF	Interoperable Global Trust Federation
IMIS	Integrated Marine Information System
IMK	Institute of Meteorology and Climate Research
IMPRS	International Max Planck Research School

IMPRS-ESM	IMPRS on Earth System Modelling
IMPRS-gBGC	International Max Planck Research School for Global BioGeoChemical Cycles
INFRADEV-4	Subcall of H2020 INFRADEV call for Implementation and operation of cross-cutting services and solutions for clusters of ESFRI and other relevant research infrastructure initiatives
INFRASUPP	European Horizon 2020 work programme
INGV	Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia
INRA	Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique
INRAE	Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'alimentation et l'Environnement
INSB	Institutul National de Cercetare Dezvoltare pentru Stiinte Biologice
INSPIRE	INfrastructure for SPatial InfoRmation in Europe
Instrument Controller	An integrated raw data source
INSU	Institut National des Sciences de l'Univers
INTERACT	International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic
Interdisciplinary	Integrating knowledge and methods from different disciplines, using a real synthesis of approaches
Intermagnet	A global network of observatories, monitoring the Earth's magnetic field
Intradisciplinary	Working within a single discipline
IODE	International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange
IoT	The Internet of Things - is a scenario in which objects, animals or people are provided with unique identifiers and the ability to transfer data over a network without requiring human-to-human or human-to-computer interaction.
IP	1) Implementation Phase 2) Internet Protocol 3) Intellectual Property
IPBES	Intergovernmental Platform on Biodiversity & Ecosystem Services
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IRI	Internationalized Resource Identifiers
IRIS	Incorporated Research Institutions for Seismology
IRISCC	Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change risks
iRODS	Integrated Rule-Oriented Data System (iRODS) is an Open Source Data Management Software.
IS	Information System
ISC	Interface and Synthesis Centre of the AnaEE Research Infrastructure
IS-ENES	RI for the European Network for Earth System Modelling
ISIC	ICOS Interim Stakeholder Council
ISIC IAGOS	Stakeholders Interim Council of IAGOS
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISO 19115	An ISO standard for metadata
ISS	International Space Station
IT	Information Technology
ITB	IT Board (of EPOS)
IUP	Institute of Environmental Physics, University of Heidelberg
IW	Internal Working data
J	
JCOMM	Joint Technical Commission for Oceanography and Marine Meteorology
JERICO	Joint European Research Infrastructure Network for Coastal Observatories
JRC	Joint Research Center
JSC	Juelich Supercomputing Centre
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data

Jupyter	Project Jupyter is a nonprofit organization created to develop open-source software, open-standards, and services for interactive computing across dozens of programming languages.
Jupyter hub	A multi-user Hub that spawns, manages, and proxies multiple instances of the single-user Jupyter notebook server
Jupyter Notebook	A Jupyter Notebook (formerly IPython Notebooks) is a web-based interactive computational environment for creating Jupyter notebook documents. The "notebook" term can colloquially make reference to many different entities, mainly the Jupyter web application, Jupyter Python web server, or Jupyter document format depending on context. A Jupyter Notebook document is a JSON document, following a versioned schema, and containing an ordered list of input/output cells which can contain code, text (using Markdown), mathematics, plots and rich media, usually ending with the ".ipynb" extension.
K	
K8s	Kubernetes
KB	Knowledge Base
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KIT	Karlsruhe Institut für Technologie
KNMI	Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut
Knowledge Base	1) A store of information or data that is available to draw on. 2) The underlying set of facts, assumptions, and rules which a computer system has available to solve a problem
Knowledge infrastructure	robust networks of people, artifacts, and institutions that generate, share, and maintain specific knowledge about the human and natural worlds
KOS	Knowledge Organisation Systems - is a generic term used in knowledge organisation about authority lists, classification systems, thesauri, topic maps, ontologies etc.
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
Kubernetes	An open-source system for automating deployment, scaling, and management of containerised applications

L

LA	Leibniz Association
LGM	French Company responsible for IAGOS Instrument manufacturing
LHT	Lufthansa Technik AG
LIDAR	Light Detecting and Ranging
LifeWatch	European e-Science infrastructure for biodiversity and ecosystem research
LifeWatch ERIC	European e-Science infrastructure for biodiversity and ecosystem research, European Research Infrastructure Consortium
LIRMM	Laboratoire d'Informatique, de Robotique et de Microélectronique de Montpellier
LLM	Large Language Model
LMS	Learning Management System
LMU	Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München
LOD	Linked Open Data
Loi	Letter of Intent
LOV	Linked Open Vocabularies
LSCE	Laboratoire des Sciences du Climat et l'Environnement
LTER	Long-term Ecosystem Research network (national)
LTER-EUROPE	European Long-term Ecosystem Research network of 21 national LTER networks
LTP	Linked Third Party
LTS	Long-Term Sustainability
LTSER	Long Term Socio-Ecological Research
LTU	a German airline
LU	Lund University (ULUND)
LW	LifeWatch
M	
M	Month

M2M	Machine-to-Machine
M4M	Metadata for Machines
MACC	Monitoring Atmospheric Composition and Climate
MACE	Middeck Active Control Experiment (Payload on ISS)
Mailchimp	An American marketing automation platform and email marketing service
Mapping Rule	Configuration directives used for model-to-model transformation.
Marcator ocean	French center for analysis and forecasting of the global ocean
Marine-ID	Registration and authentication services for marine data services
MARIS	MARiene Informatie Service
MATCH-MPIC	Model of Atmospheric Transport and Chemistry - Max Planck Institute for Chemistry version
MBA	Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom
MDA	Marine Data Archive
Measurement Model Designer	An active role, which is a person who designs the measurements and monitoring models based on the requirements of environmental scientists
Measurement result	Quantitative determinations of magnitude, dimension and uncertainty to the outputs of observation instruments, sensors (including human observers) and sensor networks.
Measurer	An active role, which is a person who determines the ratio of a physical quantity, such as a length, time, temperature etc., to a unit of measurements, such as the meter, second or degree Celsius
MediaWiki	A free and open-source wiki engine
Mentimeter	Mentimeter is a Swedish company based in Stockholm that develops and maintains an eponymous app used to create presentations with real-time feedback.
MERLIN	Methane Remote Sensing Lidar Mission
MESSy	Modular Earth Submodel System

Metadata	Data that describes and gives further information on other data. Metadata summarises basic information about data, which can make finding and working with particular instances of data easier.
Metadata Catalogue	A collection of metadata, usually established to make the metadata available to a community. A metadata catalogue has an access service.
Metadata Harvester (Publishing Community Role)	A passive role performed by a system or service collecting metadata to support the construction/selection of a global conceptual model and the production of mapping rules
Metadata Harvesting (Publishing Community Role)	A behaviour performed by a metadata harvester to gather metadata from data objects in order to construct catalogues of the available information. A functionality that (regularly) collects metadata (in agreed formats) from different sources.
Metadata State: Published	Metadata made available to the public, the outside world. Within some metadata catalogues registered
Metadata State: Raw	Established metadata, which are not yet registered. In general, they are not shareable in this status
Metadata State: Registered	Metadata which are inserted into a metadata catalogue
METEOSAT	Geostationary Weather Satellite
METOP-A/B/C	European Meteorological Polar-Orbit Satellites (A: launched 2006, B: May 2012, C: October-November 2016)
MF	Météo-France
MFT	Marine Flux Towers
MICS	Minimum Information standard for Digital Collections
MIDS	Minimum Information standard for Digital Specimens
MIG	Metadata Interest Group
MIPAS	Michelson Interferometer for Passive Atmospheric Sounding
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (Payload of TERRA and AQUA)
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
MOODA	Module of Oceanic Observatory Data Analysis

Moodle	Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
MOZAIC	Measurements of Ozone, Water Vapour, Carbon Monoxide and Nitrogen Oxides with In-service Airbus Aircraft
MPG	Max-Planck-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der Wissenschaften e.V. (english: Max Planck Society)
MPG-BGC	Max-Planck-Institut für Biogeochemie, Jena
MPI	Max Planck Institute
MPI-C	Max Planck Institute for Chemistry, Mainz
MS	MileStone
MSAs	Monitoring Station Assemblies for ICOS ERIC Member countries' Atmosphere station, Ecosystem station and Ocean station networks
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
MST	Management Support Team
Multidisciplinary	People from different disciplines working together, each drawing on their disciplinary knowledge
MVE	Minimum Valuable EOSC
N	
N ₂ O	Nitrous Oxide
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NATURALIS	Sichting Naturalis Biodiversity Center
NCAR	National Center for Atmospheric Research, Boulder, USA
NCDiS	National Committee for Data in Science
NCI	National Computational Infrastructure (Australia)
NDACC	Network for the Detection of Atmospheric Composition Change
NECTAR	Network on European Communications and Transport Activities Research
NEON	National Science Foundation's National Ecological Observatory Network

NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
NetAPP	An American hybrid cloud data services and data management company
NetCDF	A file format
NGI	National Grid Initiative
NGO	Non-governmental Organisation
NGR	Next Generation Repositories
NIES	National Institute for Environmental Studies
NILU	Norsk Institutt for Luftforskning Stiftelse
NMI	National Metrological Institutes
NNs	ICOS National Networks
NO	Nitric Oxide
NO ₂	Nitrogen Dioxide
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NOC	National Oceanography Centre
NODC	National Oceanographic Data Committee of the Netherlands
NOOA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NO _x	NO + NO ₂
NO _y	The sum of NO and its atmospheric oxidation products
NPF	New Particle Formation
NREN	National research and Education Network
NRT	Near Real Time
NVS	NERC Vocabulary Services
O	
O ₃	Ozone
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting

OAIS	Open Archival Information System
OASIS	Organisation for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards (non-profit consortium)
OAUTH	Open Authorisation (standard)
OBIS	Ocean Biogeographic Information System
OBO	Open Biological and Biomedical Ontology
OBOE	Extensible Observation Ontology
Observer	An active role, which is a person who receives knowledge of the outside world through the senses, or records data using scientific instruments
OceanSITES	A worldwide system of long-term, open-ocean reference stations measuring dozens of variables and monitoring the full depth of the ocean from air-sea interactions down to the seafloor
OCRE	Open Clouds for Research Environments
ODIP	Ocean Data Interoperability Platform
ODP	Open Distributed Processing
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OGC CSW	Open Geospatial Consortium - Catalogue Service Web
OGC or OGCO	Open Geospatial Consortium
OGC SOS	Open Geospatial Consortium - Sensor Observation Service
OGS	Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale
OIDC	OpenID Connect
OIL-E	Open Information Linking for Environmental Research Infrastructures - is a semantic linking framework. It is the ontology of the ENVRI Reference Model.
OKFN	Open Knowledge Foundation
OMG	Object Management Group

ONDA	A platform enabling users to host data and to build their applications in the Cloud
Ontology	(In computer science and information science) an ontology is a formal naming and definition of the types, properties, and interrelationships of the entities that really or fundamentally exist for a particular domain of discourse.
Ontowiki	A free and open-source semantic wiki application, meant to serve as an ontology editor and a knowledge acquisition system.
OOI	Ocean Observatories Initiative
Open Data	Open data is the idea that some data should be freely available to everyone to use and republish as they wish, without restrictions from copyright, patents or other mechanisms of control.
Open Semantic Search	A free software for building own Search Engine, an explorer for discovery of large document collections, media monitoring, text analytics, document analysis & text mining platform based on Apache Solr or Elasticsearch.
OpenAIRE	A network of Open Access repositories, archives and journals that support Open Access policies
OpenDAP	Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol
openDS	Open Digital Specimen standard
OPM	Open Provenance Model
ORCHESTRA	Open Architecture and Spatial Data Infrastructure for Risk Management
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
ORE	Open Research Europe
ORFEUS	European infrastructure for seismic waveform data and station metadata
ORM	OGC Reference Model
OSCARS	Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society
OSF	Open Science Framework
OSI	Open Systems Interconnection
OTC	Oceanic Thematic Centre of ICOS

OTN	Optical Transport Network
Over dispersion	A statistical characteristic of data such that the data have more clusters than compared to what might be expected if the data were distributed randomly in proportion to the time/space available
OWL	Web Ontology Language
P	
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PANGAEA	Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science (Open Access library aimed at archiving, publishing and distributing georeferenced data from earth system research)
PANOSC	Photon and Neutron Open Science Cloud, a Horizon 2020 project
Passive Role	A passive role is typically associated with a non-human actor
pCO ₂	Partial pressure of carbon dioxide (in the ocean)
Perform Mapping	Execute transformation rules for values (mapping from one unit to another unit) or translation rules for concepts (translating the meaning from one conceptual model to another conceptual model, e.g. translating code lists)
Perform Measurement or Observation	Measure parameter(s) or observe an event; the performance of a measurement or observation produces measurement results
Persistent Data	Term (data) used as defined in ISO/IEC 10746-2; data is the representations of information dealt by information systems and users thereof; data which are persistent (stored).
PGGM	Pacific Greenhouse Gases Measurement Project
PI	Principal Investigator
PID	Permanent (or Persistent) Identifier
PID Generator	A passive role, a system which assigns persistent global unique identifiers to a (set of) digital object
PID Registry	A passive role, which is an information system for registering PIDs
PID Service	External service for persistent identifier assignment and resolution
PKA	Personalised Knowledge Agent
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure

plc	Public Limited Company
PLOCAN	Consortio Para el Diseno, Construccion, Equipamiento y Explotacion de la Plataforma Oceanica de Canarias
PM	Person Month
PMA	Policy Management Authority
PMO	Project Management Office
PMT	Project Management Team
PO	Project Office(r) / Project Objective
PoC	Proof of Concept
Policy Maker	An active role, a person, who makes decisions based on the data evidences (synonym: Decision Maker)
POPD	Protection of Personal Data
PostgreSQL	A free and open-source relational database management system (RDBMS) emphasizing extensibility and SQL compliance
PP	Preparatory Phase
PPT	PowerPoint
PRACE	Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe
PREMIER	Process Exploration through Measurements of Infrared and Millimetre-wave Emitted Radiation (Payload on ATMOSAT)
Process Control	A functionality that receives input status, applies a set of logic statements or control algorithms, and generates a set of analogue / digital outputs to change the logic states of devices
Process Controller	Part of the execution platform provided by the data processing subsystem
Process Data	Process data for the purposes of:
PROV	Provenance
Provenance	Provenance is information about entities, activities, and people involved in producing a piece of data or thing, which can be used to form assessments about its quality, reliability or trustworthiness. The PROV Family of Documents defines a model, corresponding serializations and other supporting definitions to enable the inter-

operable interchange of provenance information in heterogeneous environments such as the Web.

PROV-O	Web Ontology Language encoding of the PROV Data Model
PTFE	Polytetrafluoroethylen, commonly known brand name of PTFE-based formulas is Teflon and used as a non-reactive coating material
PTR-MS	Proton Transfer Reaction Mass-Spectrometer
Publish Data	Make data publicly accessible
Publish Metadata	Make the registered metadata available to the public
PWG	Policy Working Group
Q	
Q	Quarter
QA	1) Quality Assurance 2) Quality Assessment
QA Notation	Notation of the result of a Quality Assessment. This notation can be a nominal value out of a classification system up to a comprehensive (machine readable) description of the whole QA process.
QA/QC	Quality Assurance (or Assessment) / Quality Control
QC	Quality Control
QoE	Quality of user Experience
QSAR	Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship
Quality Assessment	Assessment of details of the data generation, including the check of the plausibility of the data. Usually the quality assessment is done by predefined checks on data and their generation process.
Query Data	Send a request to a data store to retrieve required data
Query Metadata	Send a request to metadata resources to retrieve metadata of interests
R	
RAG	Retrieval of Augmented Generation
Raw Data Collector	Binding object for raw data collection
RBINS	Institut Royal des Sciences Naturelles de Belgique

RCN	Research Council of Norway (Norges Forskningsradet)
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDBMS	Relational DataBase Management System
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFLib	RDF Python library
RDM	Research Data Management
REA	Research Executive Agency, is an executive agency established by the European Commission in order to manage specific Community activities in the field of research and innovation. The REA's mission is to assist the Commission in achieving the objectives of the Research Framework Programmes and the EU strategies to foster growth through research and innovation. (source: Wikipedia)
Reference Model	A reference model is an abstract framework for understanding significant relationships among the entities of some environment
Register Metadata	Enter the metadata into a metadata catalogue
Repository	Data Publication Repository; a passive role, which is a facility for the deposition of published data
Research Infrastructure	means facilities, resources and related services that are used by the scientific community to conduct top-level research in their respective fields and covers major scientific equipment or sets of instruments; knowledge-based resources such as collections
Researcher	Scientist; an active role, which is a person who makes use of the data and application services to conduct scientific research
Resource Registration	A functionality that creates an entry in a resource registry and inserts a resource object or a reference to a resource object in specified representations and semantics
REST	Representational State Transfer
RESTful API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface
RHD	Relative Detected Humidity
RI	Research Infrastructure
RICOM	Research Infrastructure Committee

RI-VIS	Expanding research infrastructure visibility to strengthen strategic partnerships, H2020 project coordinated by INSTRUCT ERIC
RM	Reference Model - is an abstract framework or domain-specific ontology consisting of an interlinked set of clearly defined concepts produced by an expert or body of experts in order to encourage clear communication
RM-OA	Reference Model for the ORCHESTRA Architecture
RM-ODP	Reference Model of Open Distributed Processing (RM-ODP) is a reference model in computer science, which provides a co-ordinating framework for the standardisation of open distributed processing (ODP)
Role	A role in a community is a prescribing behaviour that can be performed any number of times concurrently or successively
RoP	Roles of Participation
RP	Reporting Period
RPO	Research Performing Organisation(s)
RR	Rolls Royce
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
RSS	Really Simple Syndication
RTD	1) Resistance Temperature Detector 2) Research and Technological Development
RTTU	Real Time Transmission Unit
S	
S3	Smart Specialisation Strategies
SA	Scientific Association (legal entity type)
SaaS	Software as a Service
SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
SABER	Sounding of the Atmosphere using Broadband Emission Radiometry (Payload on TIMED)
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language

SAR	Structure-Activity Relationship
SATD	Satellite Data
SBSTA	Subsidiary Body for Scientific and Technical Advice
SCAPE	SCAlable Preservation Environments (FP7 project)
SCC	Service Coordination Committee
SCIAMACHY	Scanning Imaging Absorption Spectrometer for Atmospheric Chartography (Payload on ENVISAT)
SciCAR	Science of Computer Assisted Reporting
Science Gateway	Community portal for interacting with an infrastructure
Scientific Modelling and Simulation	A functionality that supports the generation of abstract, conceptual, graphical or mathematical models, and to run an instance of the model
Scientific Workflow Enactment	A specialisation of Workflow Enactment, which supports composition and execution of a series of computational or data manipulation steps, or a workflow, in a scientific application. Important processes should be recorded for provenance purposes.
Scientist	Researcher; an active role, which is a person who makes use of the data and application services to conduct scientific research
SDB	Solid Earth subDomain Board
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SDLC	Software Development Life Cycle
SDMS	SIOS Data Management System
SDN	SeaDataNet
SDTS	Spatial Data Transfer Standard
SeaDataNet	Pan-European infrastructure for ocean & marine data management
Security Service	Oversight service for authentication and authorisation of user requests to the infrastructure
Semantic Annotation	A link from an information object (single datum, data set, data container) to a concept within a conceptual model, enabling the discovery of the meaning of the information object by human and machine

Semantic Broker	Broker for establishing semantic links between concepts and bridging queries between semantic domains
Semantic Laboratory	Community proxy for interacting with semantic models
Semantic Mediator	A passive role, which is a system or middleware facilitating semantic mapping discovery and integration of heterogeneous data
Semantic Mediawiki	Semantic MediaWiki is an extension to MediaWiki that allows for annotating semantic data within wiki pages, thus turning a wiki that incorporates the extension into a semantic wiki.
Semantics	The encoding of meaning using a formal language.
Sensor	A passive role, which is a converter that measures a physical quantity and converts it into a signal which can be read by an observer or by an (electronic) instrument
Sensor Network	A passive role, which is a network that consists of distributed autonomous sensors to monitor physical or environmental conditions.
SensorML	The primary focus of the Sensor Model Language is to provide a robust and semantically-tied means of defining processes and processing components associated with the measurement and post-measurement transformation of observations.
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
Service	Service or process, available for reuse
Service Consumer	Either an active or a passive role, which is an entity using the services provided
Service Description	Services and processes, which are available for reuse, be it within an enterprise architecture, within a research infrastructure or within an open network like the Internet, shall be described to help avoid wrong usage. Usually such descriptions include the accessibility of the service, the description of the interfaces, the description of behaviour and/or implemented algorithms. Such descriptions are usually done along service description standards (e.g. WSDL, web service description language). Within some service description languages, semantic descriptions of the services and/or interfaces are possible (e.g. SAWSDL, Semantic Annotations for WSDL).
Service Provider	Either an active or a passive role, which is an entity providing the services to be used
Service Registry	A passive role, which is an information system for registering services

Setup Mapping Rules	Specify the mapping rules of data and/or concepts
SF6	Sulphur hexafluoride
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
SHARC IG	SHAring Rewards and Credit Interest Group
SIOS	Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System
SIP	Submission Information Package
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organisation System
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SME	Small or Medium (-sized) Enterprise(s)
SMTP	Simple Mail Transfer Protocol
SNT	Sabena Technics
SO2	Sulfur Dioxide
SOA	1) Service Oriented Architecture 2) Secondary Organic Aerosol
SOA-RM	Reference Model for Service Oriented Architecture
SOCAT	Surface Ocean CO2 Atlas
Solr	Solr (pronounced "solar") is an open-source enterprise-search platform, written in Java, from the Apache Lucene project. (Source: Wikipedia)
SOOP	Ship of Opportunity
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
SP	Strategic priority
SPARQL	SPARQL is an RDF query language—that is, a semantic query language for databases—able to retrieve and manipulate data stored in Resource Description Framework format.
Specification of Investigation Design	This is the background information needed to understand the overall goal of the measurement or observation. It could be the sampling design of observation stations, the network design, the description of the setup parameters (interval of measurements) and so on... It usually contains important information for the allowed evaluations of data. (E.g. the question whether a sampling design was done

	randomly or by strategy determines which statistical methods that can be applied or not).
Specification of Measurements or Observations	The description of the scientific measurement model which specifies: what is measured; how it is measured; by whom it is measured; and what the temporal design is (single /multiple measurements / interval of measurement etc.)
Specify Investigation Design	Specify design of investigation, including sampling design: geographical position of measurement or observation (site) -- the selections of observations and measurement sites, e.g., can be statistical or stratified by domain knowledge; characteristics of site; preconditions of measurements
Specify Measurement or Observation	Specify the details of the method of observations/measurements
SRIA	Strategic Innovation and Research Agenda
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
SSO	Single Sign On
StaaS	Storage as a Service
Stakeholder	An active role, a person, who makes use of the data and application service for predicting market so as to make a business decision on producing related commercial products (synonyms: Private Investor, Private Consultant)
STC	Supplemental Type Certificate
Storage	A passive role, which is memory, components, devices and media that retain digital computer data used for computing for some interval of time
Storage Administrator	An active role, which is a person who has the responsibilities to design of data storage, tune queries, perform backup and recovery operations, raid mirrored arrays, making sure drive space is available for the network
Store Data	Archive or preserve data in a persistent manner to ensure continuing accessibility and usability
subdomain	In the ENVRI cluster this means the domains atmosphere, marine, solid earth and biodiversity / terrestrial ecosystems.
Subsystem	A set of capabilities that collectively are defined by a set of interfaces with corresponding operations that can be invoked by other

	subsystems. Subsystems can be executed independently, and developed and managed incrementally.
SURFSARA	SURFsara is the Dutch National High Performance Computing centre.
SV Community Behaviour	A behaviour enabled by a Semantic Mediator that unifies similar data (knowledge) models based on the consensus of collaborative domain experts to achieve better data (knowledge) reuse and semantic interoperability
sVOC	semi Volatile Organic Compound
SWFS	Scientific WorkFlow System
SWIRRL	A UK based company which publishes open government data so you can check its provenance, work with it across organisations and use it programmatically to inform your policy and strategy decisions
SWOT	analysis on Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
Syntax	In computer science, the syntax of a computer language is the set of rules that defines the combinations of symbols that are considered to be a correctly structured document or fragment in that language.
T	
T	Task
TC	Technology Centre of the AnaEE Research Infrastructure
TCCON	Total Carbon Column Observing Network
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TCS	Thematic Core Services
Technician	An active role, which is a person who develops and deploys the sensor instruments, establishes and tests the sensor network, operates, maintains, monitors and repairs the observatory hardware
TERN	Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Infrastructure, Australia
TERRA	Earth Observing Satellite (launched on December 18, 1999)
TF	Task Force
TGIR	Trés Grande Infrastructure de la Recherche

THREDDS	The THREDDS Data Server (TDS) is a web server that provides metadata and data access for scientific datasets, using OPeNDAP, OGC WMS and WCS, HTTP, and other remote data access protocols.
TIB	Technische Informationsbibliothek
TIMED	Thermosphere, Ionosphere, Mesosphere, Energetics & Dynamics Satellite (launched December 7, 2001)
TN	Training need: the gap between the current level and type of knowledge, skills, mindset, and practices, and the desired one.
TNA	Trans-National Access
TOAD	A database management toolset from Quest Software for managing relational and non-relational databases using SQL aimed at database developers, database administrators, and data analysts
ToR	Terms of Reference
TP	Third Party
Track Provenance	Add information about the actions and the data state changes as data provenances
Training Need	The gap between the current level and type of knowledge, skills, mindset, and practices, and the desired one
Transdisciplinary	Creating a unity of intellectual frameworks beyond the disciplinary perspectives
Triple	A triple is a data entity composed of subject-predicate-object
Triplestores	A triplestore or RDF store is a purpose-built database for the storage and retrieval of triples through semantic queries.
TSM	Total Suspended Matter
U	
UCAM	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Cambridge UEA University of East Anglia
UCPH	Kobenhavns Universitet (Copenhagen University)
UEDIN	University of Edinburgh
UGOT	University of Gothenburg (Goeteborgs Universitet)
UHEL	University of Helsinki (Helsingin Yliopisto)

UI	User Interface
UI/UX	User Interface / User Experience
UiB	Universitetet i Bergen (University of Bergen)
UiT	Universitetet i Tromsø (University of Tromsø)
UKRI	United Kingdom Research and Innovation
ULUND	Lunds Universitet
UMAN	University of Manchester
UML	Unified Modelling Language
UML4ODP	Unified Modelling Language For Open Distributed Processing
UN	United Nations
UN SDG methodology 14.3.1	United Nations Sustainable Development Goal Methodology 14.3.1: Average marine acidity (pH) measured at agreed suite of representative sampling stations
UNAVCO	University NAVSTAR Consortium - a non-profit university-governed consortium that facilitates geoscience research and education using Geodesy
UNECE ICP	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe - International Cooperative Programme
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
UNFCCC	UN Framework Convention on Climate Change
UniHB	Universitaet Bremen (University of Bremen)
UNILE	Universita del Salento (University of Salento)
Unique Identifier (UID)	With reference to a given (possibly implicit) set of objects, a unique identifier (UID) is any identifier which is guaranteed to be unique among all identifiers used for those objects and for a specific purpose.
UNITUS	Universita Degli Studi della Tuscia
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

User Behaviour Tracking	A behaviour enabled by a Data Use Subsystem that tracks the users; user Behaviour Tracking is the analysis of visitor behaviour on a website. The analysis of an individual visitor's behaviour may be used to provide options or content that relates to their implied preferences; either during a visit or in future visits. In addition, it can be used to track content use and performance.
User Group Work Supporting	A behaviour enabled by a Data Use Subsystem that supports controlled sharing, collaborative work and publication of results, with persistent and externally citable PIDs
User Profile Management	A behaviour enabled by a Data Use Subsystem that supports persistent and mobile profiles, where profiles will include preferred interaction settings, preferred computational resource settings, and so on
User Working Relationships Management	A behaviour enabled by a Data Use Subsystem that supports a record of working relationships, (virtual) group memberships and friends
User Working Space Management	A behaviour enabled by a Data Use Subsystem that supports work spaces that allow data, document and code continuity between connection sessions and accessible from multiple sites or mobile smart devices
USTAN	The University Court of the University of St. Andrews (University of St Andrews)
USTIR	University of Sterling
UT/LS	Upper Troposphere/Lower Stratosphere
UUID	Universally Unique IDentifier
UV	Unmanned Vehicles
UvA	Universiteit van Amsterdam
UVSQ	Université de Versailles Saint-Quentin-en-Yvelines
V	
VAAC	Volcanic Ash Advisory Centre
VC	Video Conference
VCP	(ENVRI) Virtual Community Platform
VDP	Virtual Data Product

VERCE	Virtual Earthquake and seismology Research Community e-science Environment FP7 project
Virtual Laboratory	Community proxy for interacting with infrastructure subsystems
Virtual Research Environment (VRE)	Synonyms: Science Gateway, Collaboratory, Digital Library, Inhabited Information Space, Virtual Laboratory): a web-based working environment tailored to serve the needs of a research community. A VRE is expected to provide an array of commodities needed to accomplish the research community's goal(s); it is open and flexible with respect to the overall service offering and lifetime; and it promotes fine-grained controlled sharing of both intermediate and final research results by guaranteeing ownership, provenance and attribution.
visualisation	e.g., alpha-numerically, graphically, geographically
VL or Vlab	Virtual Laboratory
VM	Virtual Machine
VOC	Volatile Organic Compound[s]
VODAN	Virus Outbreak Data Network
VOMS	Virtual Organisation Membership Service
VOS/SOOP	Voluntary Observing Ships / Ship of Opportunity Programme
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
W	
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WDS	World Data System
webGIS	web-based GIS (Geographical Information System)
WFD	European Water Framework Directive
WFMS	WorkFlow Management System
WF-t	Workflow tool element of the Analytical Framework (AF)
WG	Working Group
WG I-ADOPT	Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology Working Group

WIGOS	WMO Integrated Global Observing System
Wikidata	A collaboratively edited multilingual knowledge graph hosted by the Wikimedia Foundation.
WIS	WMO Information System
WMC	World Meteorological Centre
WMO	World Meteorological Organization
WMO-GAW	World Meteorological Organization Global Atmosphere Watch
WMS	Workflow Management System
Workflow Enactment	Scientific Workflow Enactment; a specialisation of Workflow Enactment, which supports composition and execution of a series of computational or data manipulation steps, or a workflow, in a scientific application. Important processes should be recorded for provenance purposes.
WoRMS	World Register of Marine Species
WP	Work Package
WPS	Web Processing Services
WS	Workshop
X	
XML	Extensible Markup Language
XPATH	XML Path Language, a query language
Y	
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language (YAML) is a human-readable data-serialisation language.
YaT	YAML Template
Z	
ZENODO	A general-purpose open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN

